

ALLOCATED ZONES FOR STURGEON MARICULTURE IN BULGARIAN BLACK SEA WATERS

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Abstract. In recent years, the role of cultivation of various aquatic organisms, in mariculture to reduce the anthropogenic pressure on natural fish populations is extremely important, especially for species with reduced abundance, including sturgeons – family Acipenseridae. Technologies for growing different fish species in fresh and saltwater are constantly improving and the yields are increasing. In Bulgaria, sturgeon farming is very well developed, but exclusively in freshwater. The Black Sea is not used in this direction, despite the potential it has as a water basin. Allocated Zones for Aquaculture (AZA) are essential for the rational utilisation of the sea coast and the maritime space. The overall assessment is that AZA is a key tool for the development of aquaculture activities in the Black Sea countries. Some obvious differences can be observed between the countries in terms of environmental conditions, management, technical capacity, aquaculture development, and knowledge. These differences are also reflected in the development, implementation, and management of AZA. Besides, AZA provides added value, guarantees for the future, legal stability for aquaculture. Cage fish farms in Bulgarian marine area, which in general can be located near the shore – ‘inshore’, ‘coastal’ or at a greater distance from it – ‘offshore’. The number of environmental factors, antropogenic impacts, bottom relief and possible spatial and temporal conflicts of different activities should be taken into account in AZA application in Bulgarian marine area.

Keywords: mariculture, fish, sturgeons, Black Sea, AZA, management.

AIMS AND BACKGROUND

The Mediterranean and the Black Sea stand out for their uniqueness in terms of environment, sociological and economic characteristics, and aquaculture in them has a long history in coastal communities¹. The ecosystem approach to aquaculture provides the conceptual guideline for spatial planning and management². Aquacul-

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ture plays an important role in terms of contribution to economic development and it represents an important source of food and employment for coastal communities of GFCM Members³. Allocated zones for aquaculture (AZAs) within marine spatial planning (MSP) are essential for the sustainable development and expansion of aquaculture in the Mediterranean and the Black Sea. A process for aquaculture site selection and carrying capacity estimation within the framework of an ecosystem approach to aquaculture was initially elaborated by Ref.4. The process of spatial planning usually consists of the following three steps: (i) Aquaculture zoning: bringing together the criteria for locating aquaculture and other activities in order to define broad zones suitable for different activities or mixes of activities; (ii) Site selection: identifying the most appropriate locations for individual farm development within zones; (iii) Aquaculture management areas (AMAs): within zones, AMAs contain a number of individual farms that share a common water supply and/or are in such proximity that disease and water quality are best managed collectively rather than by individual farms. An aquaculture zone can be all or part of any hydrological system that is at least partly suitable for aquaculture, whether it be the open ocean (normally within the exclusive economic zone), a bay, part of a river or estuary, or any inland water body³ as an important adaptation measure. The effectiveness of zoning depends upon its simplicity, clarity and degree of local support. Marine aquaculture zoning through an ecosystem approach and considering climate variability and change is encouraged by was a traditional activity in Bulgaria. Most of the catch used to come from the Danube River, with only 10% from the Black Sea^{5,6}. According to Ref. 5, all sturgeon populations in Bulgaria have decreased drastically, with the ship sturgeon and European sturgeon apparently extinct. Despite errors of assessment of real catch, a general trend of rapid decline of breeding stock is observed; in the Danube River catches were recorded juvenile specimens of *Acipenser gueldenstaedti* (12–18 cm); juvenile individuals caught were 1% from the total catch of the Acipenseridae⁷.

EXPERIMENTAL

Several geospatial data sets and layers were used in the process of the GIS-aided spatial suitability analysis (Fig. 1). These are indicated in Table 1.

Table 1. Layers and geospatial data for the GIS-aided spatial suitability analysis

Data set/layer	Format (type)	Source
Terrestrial and marine borders of Bulgaria	ESRI shapefile (polyline)	archive of IO-BAS
Fairways and main ship traffic routes	ESRI shapefile (polyline)	archive of IO-BAS
Present-day coastline	ESRI shapefile (polyline)	Kotsev and Prodanov (unpublished material)
25- and 50 m bathymetric contours	ESRI shapefile (polyline)	contours derived from the EMODNET bathymetry for the Black Sea
Marine buffer 5 nautical miles offshore	ESRI shapefile (polygon)	generated by the authors for the purpose of the study herein
NATURA 2000 protected sites: Birds and Habitats directives; other nationally designated marine protected areas	ESRI shapefile (polygon)	http://eea.government.bg/zpo/en/index.jsp
Spoil grounds	ESRI shapefile (polygon)	archive of IO-BAS
Forbidden areas	ESRI shapefile (polygon)	archive of IO-BAS
Heavy-traffic marine areas	ESRI shapefile (polygon)	EMODNET Black Sea Checkpoint (http://emodnet-blacksea.eu/)
Seabed substrates	ESRI shapefile (polygon)	archive of IO-BAS
Seafloor geomorphology	ESRI shapefile (polygon)	archive of IO-BAS

Marine use types, bathymetry, seabed substrates, bed forms and distance offshore played an important role in the geospatial suitability analysis for identification of areas potentially suitable for sturgeon farming. The main criteria applied in the GIS-aided overlay analysis were: Areas should be outside the boundaries of sites belonging to the national ecological network (i.e. NATURA 2000 protected sites designated in compliance with the Birds and Habitats directives, or nationally designated protected areas); areas should be outside the boundaries of forbidden zones, anchorage areas and harbour areas, military training sites, spoil grounds, heavy-traffic marine areas used for navigation; areas should be characterised by depths between 25 and 50 m; areas should be located less than 5 nautical miles offshore; the seabed should consist of loose substrata, i.e. gravel, sand or silt; the seabed sector should be of depositional type.

Fig. 1. GIS – aided spatial suitability analysis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Five potentially suitable sites for sturgeon farming were identified during the process of GIS-aided spatial suitability analysis (Fig. 2). The first site is located approximately 7.2 km south from Cape Kaliakra in the northern sector of the Bulgarian Black Sea, having an area of 684.13 ha. The seafloor represents a relic submarine terrace within the lower boundary of the underwater coastal slope. The seabed substrata consist of soft-malleable terrigenous silts with whole shells and shell fragments, accumulated at depths 30–50 m.

The second site is located approximately 3.2 km east from the Cape Paletsa-Cape Sveti Atanas coastal stretch in the central sector of the Bulgarian Black Sea, having an area of 4142.43 ha. The seafloor is again a relic submarine terrace, partially covered by depositional sand bars. The seabed substrata consist of soft-malleable terrigenous silts with whole shells and shell fragments and sandy silts within the sand bars, accumulated at depths 25–30 m.

The third site, having an area of 8788.94 ha is located some 3.5 km to the southeast of site No 2, sharing similar geomorphic and features and sedimentological properties with it, although developed at greater depths (35–40 m).

Fig. 2. Potentially suitable sites for sturgeon farming in Bulgarian marine area

The fourth site is located approximately 4.5 km to the east off the Nessebar Peninsula-Pomorie Peninsula coastline sector, South Bulgarian Black Sea, having an area of 4827.98 ha. Most of the seafloor represents an accumulative depression. The seabed substrata consist of soft-malleable with terrestrial origin silts with whole shells and shell fragments, deposited at depths 25–27 m.

The fifth site is located approximately 1.1 km south-southeast from the town of Tsarevo, South Bulgarian Black Sea, having an area of 562.97 ha. The seafloor

is again a relic submarine terrace, covered by soft-malleable with terrestrial origin silts with whole shells and shell fragments, deposited at depths 25–50 m, whether at sea or on land, aquaculture production usually requires a lot of space and access to good quality water. In many areas, conflicts arise between stakeholders who want to use the same space for different purposes, and this may limit the development potential of the aquaculture sector. Marine area use decisions can be highly controversial and lead to long-term conflicts in the local community. One of the key tools for mitigating these conflicts is spatial planning, i.e. determining what types of activities are allowed in different areas. A number of legal acts regulate planning at the level of individual Member States and sometimes at regional level. To ensure that the development of aquaculture in the Fisheries Local Action Groups (FLAGs) area is not constrained by conflicts with the use of space for aquaculture production, FLAGs need to know how spatial planning decisions are made in their Member State (or region) and who is responsible. In addition to national/regional rules, the planning process must take into account EU legislation, such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), the Water Framework Directive (WFD), the Habitats Directive, the Birds Directive and the Strategic Environmental Assessment Directive (SEA) (which concerns the plans and land use, transport, energy, waste, etc. programs adopted by public authorities at national, regional or local level), and the Impact Assessment Directive (applicable to individual projects). Recently adopted EU legislation also requires Member States to implement maritime spatial planning (MSP). There are several limiting factors for the development of aquaculture on our Black Sea coast. The natural conditions in the Black Sea differ significantly from the countries of Western Europe or other developed maritime countries in this respect. In them, aquaculture facilities are installed in well-protected areas such as estuaries, fjords, and heavily indented bays. There are no such places on the Bulgarian Black Sea coast, which necessitates the use of storm-resistant facilities in areas not protected from agitation. This undoubtedly makes the production of mariculture more expensive. A more significant factor restraining fish production is the temperature regime of the Black Sea waters in annual terms. The appropriate temperature regime for the active vegetation period of fish (feeding and growth) in the Black Sea is significantly shorter than in the Mediterranean, due to which the production of finished market products from bream and/or sea bass is the most widely farmed fish species in the Mediterranean in cages in our country requires longer cultivation (instead of one for two calendar years), which makes production more expensive and makes it uncompetitive. To this must be added the risks of production during the often very unfavourable conditions of the winter months and the weight loss due to the inability to feed the fish. Under the climatic conditions of the Romanian littoral, the experiments revealed that the growth parameters of the Russian sturgeon in marine water are superior to those regarding the farming in fresh water⁸.

Another significant factor with a negative effect on the development of marine aquaculture is the strong anthropogenic pollution, which is expressed in significant eutrophication and the appearance of 'blooms', causing 'oxygen deficiency' and 'mass deaths' in the affected areas in the coastal area. Russian sturgeon is a suitable species for breeding in net cages. The sturgeons stick to the bottom, as the individual specimens swim on the surface or near the walls of the cages, eating the plant and animal organisms clinging to the nets, and taking specialised granulated feed, and thus grow quickly. They are resistant to diseases and practically do not get sick. They are very rarely attacked by parasites. Breeding sturgeons in cages can begin after the fish have reached an average weight of over 5–10 g. The recommended planting is 20–40 pcs/m³. At the end of the growing season, sturgeons can reach 50–100 g with a survival rate of 50–60%. In the second year, the cages are stocked with no more than 12–20 pieces/m³, the fish are fed 2–3 times a day, and the survival rate is 90–95%. The average weight of the second year is of the order of 1.0–1.5 kg, and in the third, when planting about 10 pcs/m³ about 2.5 kg. Yields are in the range of 20–40 kg/m³ and vary depending on the planting, type, and quality of food and hydro chemical conditions.

Production facilities for the development of mariculture – onshore and offshore. The choice of location of marine farms is crucial for their economic viability. Choosing the right location for farms using seawater is extremely important for their efficiency. On the one hand, this is related to water quality, and on the other hand to logistics and servicing their overall activities⁹. In general, marine farms can be defined as those situated on the shore and those located directly in the marine environment (cage farms).

Complete and incomplete farms. The definition of aqua farms as complete or incomplete is done taking into account their production tasks. In full-system farms, organisms are grown in a full cycle of development and the production processes include all technological stages from reproduction to their cultivation to consumable sizes. Incomplete aquacultures are designed for growing seedlings, usually seedlings, or only individuals for consumption.

Farms located in the marine environment – cage farms. The cage farms are made of net cages, which are facilities important for aquaculture. They are floating structures located in different reservoirs, incl. and in the seas. In essence, structure and structure, cage farms differ significantly from other types of fish farms. There are several main differences, but the main one is that this form of industrial fish farming avoids the need for a continuous inflow of water and, as a rule, artificial aeration is not applied¹⁰. Growing fish in cages (net cages) is an established method for raising different species of fish¹¹. The basis on which the rearing of fish in cages is built is the provision of the main factors important for achieving high results: water temperature, amount of dissolved oxygen, quality food, and application of

dense plantings. With their optimal combination, extremely high yields can be obtained. When choosing places for construction of cage farms, it is necessary to take into account the whole complex of factors, among which the most important are the physicochemical parameters of the water, incl. temperature and oxygen regime, water exchange, as well as the strength and direction of winds, waves, etc. An obligatory condition in the design of cage farms is to study mainly the relevant area, making the necessary chemical analyses and carefully monitoring the fluctuations of the water level, the direction of winds and currents, as well as the dynamics of the hydrochemical and temperature regime. The main requirement for caged fish farming in seawater is good water quality. It must be free from industrial pollution and meet the biological requirements of the cultivated species. These criteria mainly include appropriate temperature, salinity, and dissolved oxygen⁹. The water must be free of excessive suspended solids, with limited cases of algal blooms and the presence of deceased organisms. Some current is needed to ensure adequate water exchange in the cages, but if the current is too strong, the fish can become stressed.

Pollutants. Cultivated aquatic organisms can be adversely affected by various water pollutants and sometimes directly cause certain losses. They negatively affect farmed fish, causing mortality or contamination to such an extent that the fish itself in certain cases cannot even be traded for human consumption.

Water temperature. Of the abiotic factors of the environment, temperature is of great importance for the growth of fish. For each species the highest growth is achieved within certain temperature limits. Temperature has a direct effect on fish metabolism, and hence on oxygen consumption and activity, as well as tolerance to ammonia and carbon dioxide levels⁹.

Salinity. Improper salinity levels can adversely affect nutrition, FCR, and specific growth rate (SGR). Significant variations in salinity contribute to stress, which can suppress the immune system of farm-raised fish, making them more susceptible to parasite infections and other diseases. When building farms, it should be borne in mind that estuaries are places where salinity variations are often observed and should be avoided if cultivated fish species are sensitive to differences in this specific environmental parameter.

Hydrogen index (pH). Seawater is stably buffered against pH variations and as such the pH is usually in the range of 8.0–8.2.

Turbidity. Farms should be located in areas with relatively clean water. Preferably, the suspended solids are less than 5 mg/l and do not exceed 10 mg/l. Turbid water is not suitable for fish farming for the following main reasons: sludge particles in turbid water contribute to pollution; Sludge particles in large quantities can clog fish gills, causing death by suffocation; marine cells can be of different types

(fixed, floating, fixed on buoys or pontoons, as well as submerged assault cells). However, such cells are difficult to maintain in storms.

Water exchange. The water exchange in the cages is carried out in a passive way due to the water currents, the winds and the movement of the fish. The use of various facilities for forced water exchange is practically not used. Sometimes access to fresh water is hampered by the development of so-called ‘biological fouling’, which together with the fine sludge clogs the ‘eyes’ of the net, which requires their periodic replacement or cleaning. It is known that there is a certain influence between the cages and the environment in both directions⁹ (Fig. 1). Besides, one cell may affect other cells, as currents can transfer pests, pathogens, and chemicals from one cell to another. These facts must be taken into account when choosing a location of cage farms, taking into account all possible impacts and minimising possible threats. When choosing a place for cage farms, the relief and the structure of the bottom are important. It must be studied to determine how the mesh cells are anchored and the type of anchors. Since the anchor is embedded deep in the seabed, it is important to know more not only about its surface but also about its depth structure. Shells, weeds, and seagrass can interfere with anchor attachment. A large part of the marine farms are represented by cage farms, which in general can be located near the shore – ‘inshore’ or at a greater distance from it – ‘off-shore’. Almost the entire manicures are near the coast. Offshore manicures, which are practiced on the high seas, have significant exposure to wind and waves, as well as equipment and service ships operating in severe marine conditions since its inception. Finding suitable locations is a critical part of spatial planning for the near future of offshore manicures¹². There are different classifications for the location of marine farms and in particular for those at sea. The main parameters of the environment, as well as the legal and logistical conditions when choosing a location for cage farms, are indicated in Ref. 13 (Table 2).

Table 2. Parameters and factors in choosing the location of cage farms¹³

Ecological parameters and factors related to cultivated organisms	Ecological parameters and factors related to cells	Legal/logistical criteria
Temperature	depth	legal/political aspects
Salinity	shelter, waves	access
Pollution	seabed	security
Dissolved solid matters	currents	market approximates
Algae blooms	fouling	traditional property rights
Pathogen organisms	pollution	process of obtaining a rental permit
Water exchange	–	–
Currents	–	–
Dissolved oxygen	–	–

Irrespective of the location of production facilities and ancillary buildings and facilities, the following main characteristics of the area must be taken into account and taken into account when choosing the location of marine holdings: The main physicochemical parameters of water; the danger of pollution; The direction of the winds; The excitement; the depth of the area for the location of the mariculture; presence of a sufficiently large coastal area, remote from settlements and lack of danger of domestic and industrial water pollutants; Possibility for logistical support, etc.

Depending on the location of the farms in the sea, they can be classified as coastal (< 500 m from the shore); offshore (0.5–3 km from the coast) offshore (> 2 km from the coast) (according to Ref. 9, Table 3). Other classifications are used in Norway, as this one depending on the parameters of the waves, and thus depending on their average speed¹⁴.

Table 3. Classification of aquaculture holdings⁹

Signs	Coastal	Inshore	Offshore
Location/hydrography	<500 m from the coast <10 m depth in low tide; seen from the shore; protected	0.5–3 km from shore 10–50 m depth in low tide; seldom seen from the shore; often protected	> 2 km from shore usually in continental shelf zones, possibly in open sea 50 m depths
Environment	Hs usually <1 m localised coastal currents probable strong tidal flows	Hs ≤ 3–4 m localised coastal currents some tidal flows.	Hs 5 m or more, regularly 2–3 m ocean swells; variable wind periods Less localised currents.
Access	100% accessible; mooring are possible at any time	> 90% accessible; at least once per day mooring is possible	usually > 80% accessible, possible mooring, periodically, each 3–10 days
Service	regular manual feeding surveillance, etc.	some automated operations, i.e. feeding, monitoring	remote control, automated feeding, remote monitoring

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the analysis of the limiting factors, natural conditions and options for developing the sturgeon mariculture in Bulgarian marine area, a few suitable areas suitable for cage farming have been identified. The complex factors show that

fish aquaculture holdings could be situated and function as inshore and/or coastal cage mariculture.

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